

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 9, No. 1; January 28, 2003

Dear Readers:

Here is the first issue of 2003, a bit late, but both the February and March issues are already well advanced. I am sure you will enjoy the mix of papers we have in this issue, contrasting with the fact that February and March will be dedicated to a specific topic each: the February issue presents a selection of papers from the 5th international workshop on *Tools for System Design and Verification* whereas the March issue presents the best papers from the international workshop on *Compiler Optimization Meets Compiler Verification*.

Naturally, we still need good papers for later issues, and would also like to encourage you to consider editing a special issue on a topic of your choice.

For now, enjoy reading and let us make sure that this 9th year of J.UCS will be a very special one! If we count our first issue in 1994, do you realize that we are already in year ten? This must be a record for an electronic journal!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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